

Performance and Optimization of a decentralized Resource-Oriented Sanitation System

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Abstract

This study evaluates a decentralized resource-oriented sanitation (ROS) system implemented in a rural community, designed to integrate urine separation, struvite precipitation, composting, and greywater treatment. Over five years of operation, the system demonstrated high efficiency in phosphorus and nitrogen removal, achieving over 90% phosphorus recovery and significant reductions in organic load and turbidity. Despite being designed for 16 users, the system effectively handled peak loads of up to 80 people during summer, highlighting its resilience. However, the vertical flow filter exhibited nitrification inefficiencies and sand saturation issues due to intermittent high-volume urine dosing, after five years of operation. Soil analyses confirmed major reductions in particle size, permeability and BET surface area. Future improvements focus on optimizing feeding strategies, enhancing maintenance, and exploring alternative filtration media to extend filter lifespan and improve system robustness.

Keywords (maximum 6 in alphabetical order)

Decentralized Sanitation; Nutrient Recovery; Resource-Oriented Sanitation (ROS); Source separation

INTRODUCTION

Sanitation is essential for human well-being, yet access remains inequitable, particularly in rural areas where conventional centralized wastewater treatment systems are often impractical due to high transportation costs and environmental inefficiencies. Resource-oriented sanitation (ROS) offers a transformative approach by integrating wastewater treatment with resource recovery, enabling the reuse of water and the recovery of nutrients. ROS employs diverse technologies tailored to separate and treat distinct wastewater streams at the source, such as greywater, blackwater, urine, and feces.

This study evaluates the performance of a decentralized ROS system implemented in a rural community in Rhineland-Palatinate, Germany. Designed in 2018 to accommodate an average of 16 users daily, the system employs a multi-stage approach. Greywater from household and camping activities is treated using a constructed wetland (CW), while urine from urine-diverting dry toilets is processed in a reactor to produce struvite. Feces are managed through a two-stage composting process, including rapid in-vessel composting followed by open-air post-composting. To address local groundwater protection regulations, the treated effluent flows to an evaporation pond, ensuring a zero-discharge system.

Using simple procedures, more than 90%, and often over 99%, of the phosphorus in the urine can be reliably recovered as MAP. The remaining nitrogen-rich urine supernatant is nitrified in a Vertical Flow Filter filled (VFF) with zeolite-containing lava sand. The outlet of this first filter is mixed with greywater and then routed to a constructed wetland (CW) for subsequent treatment. The use of a soil filter for nitrifying highly concentrated wastewater streams represents an innovation and a low cost improvement to high nitrogen load treatment. Although innovative, the high concentrations of Nitrogen can lead to partial nitrification as registered in this case. After five years of operation, accommodating a growing number of users at a camping site, which peaked at 80–100 people during summer months, the VFF became saturated, prompting replacement. This study has focused on evaluating the new sand filter's performance, diagnosing the causes of the previous

filter's saturation, and proposing maintenance and operational optimizations to prevent recurrence of similar issues. The concept of the system can be found at the figure 1.

Figure 1. Concept of wastewater treatment and resource recovery system at the Reinighof.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The methodology for this research involves a six-month sampling and analysis phase to evaluate the performance and resilience of the decentralized wastewater treatment system under varying operational and environmental conditions. Systematic data collection will target critical points in the system, including the inflow and outflow of the VFF, the inflow and outflow of the CW and the evaporation pond.

The sampling campaign is structured into three distinct phases. The first phase comprises an intensive five-day sampling during summer, focusing on system performance under high temperatures and peak occupancy conditions. The second phase spans four months, with biweekly sampling to capture a broader range of operational scenarios and trends. The third phase involves another intensive five-day sampling conducted in winter, assessing the system under reduced usage and more challenging environmental conditions. This phased approach ensures a comprehensive evaluation of the system's performance across diverse seasonal and occupancy contexts.

On sampling days, pH, turbidity and EC of the five samples are determined by WTW portable meters. Analysis of the parameters COD, N_{tot}, P_{tot}, NO₃-N, NO₂-N, PO₄³-P, Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻, were carried out in the lab facilities of the Technische Universität Kaiserslautern using Hach Lange LCK cuvette tests, and the cations K⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺ and Na⁺, NH₄⁺, are analysed by ion chromatography. Additionally, three VFF soil samples were analysed for BET surface, particle size distribution (PSD), Permeability (kfA) and Coefficient of Uniformity (U). These included the original sand before operation, as well samples from the saturated top and bottom layers of the filter.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The performance of the system is assessed based on key water quality parameters and nutrient removal. The results in Table 1 exhibit a wide range of values, influenced by seasonal variations in system performance. The constructed wetland and evaporation pond system demonstrated a significant reduction in pollutant concentrations across all measured parameters. The reduction in turbidity from an initial 67.3 NTU to 1.73 NTU in the final effluent indicates an efficient removal of suspended solids. Similarly, COD levels exhibited a remarkable decrease from 5046 mg/L at the inlet of the VFF to 33.1 mg/L in the final pond effluent, reflecting a high organic matter degradation efficiency. The system effectively removed TN and TP from the wastewater streams. Initial total nitrogen concentrations of 4254.6 mg/L were reduced to 10.7 mg/L in the final effluent. Ammonium nitrogen (NH₄⁺N) concentrations decreased significantly from 4569 mg/L to 0.27

mg/L, demonstrating the efficiency of the nitrification process.

		Inlet VFF	Outlet VFF	Inlet CW	Outlet CW	Pond
	Unit	Average ± Std. Dev.				
pH	-	9.4 ± 0.2	7.5 ± 0.3	7.7 ± 0.2	6.9 ± 0.1	7.7 ± 0.2
T	°C	12.8 ± 5.2	13.1 ± 5.6	14.0 ± 4.6	12.6 ± 5.9	12.5 ± 8.2
Turbidity	NTU	67.3 ± 49.9	74.3 ± 126	68.3 ± 22.5	4.6 ± 6.7	1.73 ± 1.9
Conductivity	µS/cm	28850 ± 2420	20130 ± 3820	1764 ± 469.2	1987.9 ± 361.8	903.7 ± 183.4
COD	mg/L	5046 ± 802.4	1603 ± 638.3	194.8 ± 88.02	17.4 ± 7.1	33.1 ± 11.3
TN	mg/L	4254.6 ± 689.4	2555 ± 525.9	86.5 ± 45.6	116.7 ± 41.4	10.7 ± 8.0
TP	mg/L	14.9 ± 16.01	1.58 ± 0.6	1.5 ± 0.6	0.09 ± 0.03	< 0.05
Po₄³⁻	mg/L	0.8 ± 0.6	0.2 ± 0.2	< 0,05	< 0.05	< 0.05
NO₃N-	mg/L	8.6 ± 2.7	1578.4 ± 387.6	35.7 ± 40.9	105.5 ± 39.8	9.1 ± 7.1
NO₂N-	mg/L	0.21 ± 0.2	114.4 ± 131.7	2.0 ± 4.0	0.15 ± 0.2	0.04 ± 0.03
SO₄²⁻	mg/L	939.2 ± 130.2	635.0 ± 202.7	76.6 ± 14.6	75.0 ± 18.3	< 40,0
Cl⁻	mg/L	2738.7 ± 345	1395 ± 378	119.4 ± 75.9	112.2 ± 47.4	89.7 ± 26.6
Na⁺	mg/L	1425.6 ± 212	1008 ± 271.0	123.6 ± 24.9	119.6 ± 21.1	83.4 ± 17.7
NH₄⁺N	mg/L	4569 ± 569.2	902.8 ± 495.5	65.9 ± 30.2	0.7 ± 0.4	0.27 ± 0.1
K⁺	mg/L	1530 ± 667	1094.4 ± 525	73.0 ± 28.6	35.4 ± 7.2	29.2 ± 8.2
Ca⁺	mg/L	60.9 ± 45.6	1579.2 ± 684.5	145 ± 75.9	239.3 ± 56.4	72.8 ± 18.2
Mg⁺	mg/L	129.1 ± 47.2	205.2 ± 45.0	22.8 ± 7.1	24.0 ± 5.13	13.5 ± 3.0

Table 1. Chemical and physical properties of critical points in the system.

Phosphorus recovery was also highly effective, with more than 90% of phosphorus in urine successfully precipitated as magnesium ammonium phosphate (MAP) using a struvite reactor. P total concentrations dropped from 14.9 mg/L at the system inlet to below 0.05 mg/L in the final effluent, minimizing eutrophication risks and ensuring compliance with environmental discharge regulations.

The system exhibits effective performance, with optimal treatment achieved through a two-step filtration process: initial treatment in the VFF followed by a CW. However, nitrification in the VFF remains incomplete due to high nitrogen loads. Contrary to expectations, winter did not further reduce nitrification rates, possibly due to lower system usage improving efficiency despite lower temperatures. A key factor influencing performance is the high-volume feeding dosing at the VFF, linked to struvite precipitation events (140L per dose), occurring every two days in summer and weekly in winter. This feeding pattern likely contributes to system overload, further limiting nitrification efficiency.

A comparative analysis of the specialized soil filter before and after saturation revealed significant changes in sand characteristics that can be followed at table 2. The former sand had originally favourable characteristics, including a high specific surface area and zeolite content, but after years of operation it showed clear signs of degradation. The unused sand before startup had a d10 of 0.11 mm. After filter clogging, both the top layer (d10 = 0.023 mm, U = 14.1) and the bottom layer (d10 = 0.0082 mm, U = 16.3) showed significant decreases in particle size. This suggests fine particle accumulation within the whole filter media but with a more significant accumulation of very fine

particles at the bottom, likely due to precipitate that is not consistently separated from the supernatant, thus entering the VFF system through the inlet pipe or due to precipitation occurring inside the VFF that can form salt precipitates. The finer particles and precipitates likely reduce pore spaces, leading to restricted water flow. The BET surface area also decreased with operation. The initial BET surface area was found to be 81.9 m²/g, but it decreased to 57.05 m²/g (top layer) and 57.15 m²/g (bottom layer) after filter clogging.

	U	d10	kfA	BET
	(d60/d10)	(mm)	(0,01·d102 in m/s)	(m ² /g)
Lavasand before construction	15.4	0.11	1.2·10 ⁻⁴	81.9
Top layer Lavasand after saturation	14.1	0.02	5.3·10 ⁻⁶	57.05
Bottom layer Lavasand after saturation	16.3	0.008	6.7·10 ⁻⁷	57.2

Table 2. Comparison of BET and d10 from the sand before and after use and saturation.

The decline in BET surface area and other changes in physical chemical properties of the filter material strongly suggest that precipitation processes occur inside the system or precipitates enter the system, potentially altering the filter material's composition and efficiency. The conditions within the VFF create an environment favourable to the formation of low solubility precipitates. The high concentrations of Mg²⁺, K⁺, Cl⁻, and other salts originating from urine, combined with an elevated pH of approximately 9.4 at the inlet and favourable temperatures, promote a wide array of precipitation processes. Additionally, struvite precipitates may be carried downstream by the urine supernatant, further contributing to mineral accumulation within the system.

Preventing precipitation entirely within the system presents a significant challenge. However, strategies such as enhanced separation of struvite precipitate before VFF feeding or intermittently feeding could potentially prevent clogging and mineral buildup. If the replacement becomes necessary, which is highly probable, the system as a whole is not strongly affected, since the downstream CW ensures operational continuity

Considering that the system was originally designed for 16 users but has operated for three years with peak loads of up to 80 people during the summer, it demonstrates a capacity to handle significantly higher usage than intended. This indicates the system's resilience and adaptability under varying user demands. Future enhancements to improve system robustness include modifying the feeding strategy of the specialized filter, improve maintenance protocols and exploring alternative filtration media to further increase system resilience. These improvements aim to extend the lifespan of the filter media, delaying the need for replacement, which became necessary after five years of operation.

Despite previous challenges, the system remains a promising solution for decentralized sanitation with a strong focus on resource recovery. By integrating dry-separating toilets, struvite precipitation, and nature-based treatment solutions, the system not only provides effective sanitation but also contributes to sustainable resource management, which makes ROS an ideal solution for decentralized sanitation.

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